

Deleted: QUIZ FOR COURSE 6

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ADEN MOUSSA****FIRST NAME: YOUSOUF****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

QUIZ FOR COURSE PERIOD 6

1. Reference made to Turabian (2018), on citing your source, indicate the right reasons for citing sources:

- To give credit and show readers the research tradition that informs your work.¹
- To check facts' inaccuracies in your work.
- To identify your line of thought.
- To show your writing skills.

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago, London: University of Chicago Press., 2018), 139–41.

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2. Reference made to Turabian (2018) on the requirement of citation, indicate situations requiring citations:

- When you use ideas that are different from your source.
- When you use data that are not related to your work.
- When you quote exact words from a source and any ideas, data, or methods attributable to any source you consulted.²**
- When you use methods that are not applied in your work.

3. Reference made to Turabian (2018) on the information required for citations, indicate the correct needed information:

- advertisements and promotional content of the text.
- The access date and place.
- The number of pictures and tables in it.
- Author's name, editor, publisher of the text, as well as its title, subtitle, and where it can be found.³**

4. Reference made to Turabian (2018) on the importance of accurate quotations, indicate how to use accurate quotations:

- You must provide background information.

² Turabian et al., 140–41.

³ Turabian et al., 141.

- You must use only reliable, relevant sources and transcribe words precisely as they are in the original.**⁴
 - You can rephrase all elements of the quotation.
 - You must be critical of the content of the quotation.
5. Reference made to Turabian (2018) on quotation marks, indicate how to place punctuation with the quotation marks:
- A final comma or period nearly always precedes a closing quotation mark, whether it is part of the quoted matter or not.**⁵
 - When single quotation marks are used to set off special terms in certain fields, such as linguistics, philosophy, and theology, do not put a period or comma after the closing quotation mark.
 - Question marks and exclamation points do not precede a closing quotation mark if they are part of the quoted matter.
 - Question marks do not follow the quotation mark if they apply to the entire sentence in which the quotation appears.
6. Reference made to Bloomberg (2019) on the alignment between the research problem and research approach, indicate what the goals of applied research are:
- To contribute new knowledge.
 - To extend the current theory to a new area.

⁴ Turabian et al., 370–71.

⁵ Turabian et al., 326–27.

- To complicate a problem.
- To use knowledge to contribute directly to the understanding of a problem and generate a solution for it.**⁶

7. Reference made to Bloomberg (2019) on the alignment between research methodology and research methods, indicate what are the most commonly used types of qualitative data collection:

- Interviews, observations, focus groups, and document review.**⁷
- Music albums.
- Docuseries.
- Movies.

8. Reference made to Cleenewerck and Kabiru (2021) on when to not cite, indicate what are the common situations you do not need to cite:

- When discussing the work of other researchers.
- When using specific data.
- When the information you are writing about is common knowledge, and if it is repeated in many different sources.**⁸
- When paraphrasing and restating someone idea.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019), 240–41.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 256–57.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 37.

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9. Reference made to Cleenewerck and Kabiru (2021) on the beginning of a sentence when numbers or a date are required to open a sentence, indicate what is the correct standout:

- You must write them out in a telegraphic manner.
- You must write them out in numbers.
- You must write them out all in letters.**⁹
- You must write them in Morse code.

10. Reference made to European Commission (2021) on the legal language, indicate the correct verb to use when a provision lays on an objective:

- You must use “in line with”.
 - You must use “pursuant to”.
 - You must use “in compliance”.**¹⁰
- You must use “in accordance”.

Commented [KG1]: You opted to use US English, therefore, all punctuations should be placed inside the inverted commas!

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⁹ Cleenewerck and [Gulma](#), 48.

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¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (Bruxelles, 2021), 68.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Brussels: Publication Office of the European Union, 2023.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.